

SOCIAL SCIENCES

EDUCATIONAL MEDIATION IN BULGARIA: ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE IN THE CONTEXT OF NATIONAL SECURITY AND SOCIAL STABILITY

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Abstract

Educational mediation is a key mechanism for social inclusion, student retention, and conflict resolution within educational institutions. This study examines its role in facilitating dialogue between students, teachers, and local communities, with a particular focus on marginalized and ethnic groups. The analysis highlights the connection between educational mediation and national security, emphasizing its contribution to social stability and economic development. Through a comparative analysis of international best practices, the study proposes strategic guidelines for enhancing the effectiveness of mediation mechanisms in Bulgaria.

Keywords: *educational mediation, social inclusion, school integration, conflicts in education, national security, education governance, Bulgaria*

The contemporary social dynamics lead to the emergence of various internal and social issues, driven by multiple factors, including personal negligence, low tolerance, psycho-emotional tension, socio-economic conditions, and governmental policies. According to Galtung (1996), conflicts in society arise as a result of structural, cultural, and direct forms of violence, which complicate social communication and increase the need for effective mechanisms for their resolution.

These factors reflect not only the educational and family environment but also social and cultural processes, creating spaces for both civic and institutionalized conflicts (Coleman, 2000). In times of communication crises and social tension, mediation has established itself as an effective mechanism for the voluntary resolution of conflicts. According to Bush and Folger (1994), mediation not only facilitates the achievement of consensus but also promotes a transformative approach to conflict resolution, creating conditions for the long-term improvement of interpersonal and institutional relationships.

This process relies on a third, neutral, and impartial party – the mediator – who facilitates the search for a mutually acceptable solution. As noted by Wall and Dunne (2012), the role of the mediator is not only to negotiate between the conflicting parties but also to create an environment for constructive dialogue, fostering sustainable social stability.

Mediation is an important social tool for out-of-court dispute resolution, applied in various areas of public life. According to Bush and Folger (1994), mediation plays a crucial role in fostering voluntary dialogue between parties, providing a more flexible approach to conflict resolution than the judicial system. Its integration into the educational sector is particularly significant, as educational mediation serves as a key mechanism for preventing conflicts, promoting social and educational inclusion, and ensuring student retention within the educational system (Deutsch, 2006).

Moreover, mediation is widely utilized in other fields, such as healthcare, cultural interactions, and civil disputes. Wall and Dunne (2012) emphasize that mediation across various social sectors contributes to

building a sustainable and harmonious society by reducing social tension and facilitating intercultural dialogue. In this context, mediation can be seen as a strategic tool for social stability and the nonviolent resolution of conflicts (Moore, 2014).

National security and education: interrelation and strategic approaches a) Educational mediation as a tool for strengthening national security

Educational mediation is essential for promoting social cohesion, preventing conflicts, and minimizing social risks in the context of national security threats. According to Kishkembayeva (2024), mediation facilitates reaching an agreement between two parties with the assistance of a third party – the mediator. This approach serves as a means of reducing social tension by establishing effective mechanisms for conflict resolution and social adaptation of vulnerable groups, which is also applicable within the school environment.

Mediation is one of the most effective mechanisms for fostering dialogue, promoting tolerance, integration, and social inclusion, including for vulnerable groups (Bush & Folger, 1994). School mediation in a multicultural environment creates opportunities to reduce ethnic tensions and social isolation through the active involvement of mediators in the educational process. It has been observed that conflict management methods in the school environment contribute to reducing instances of social isolation and minimizing the risk of early dropout of students up to the age of 14 from the educational system (Coleman & Deutsch, 2006).

An important milestone in the development of the Bulgarian educational system is the introduction of the newly established position of “Educational mediator” (code 53123004) by Order of the Minister of Labor and Social Policy No. RD01-715/19.09.2017. This decision is based on Article 110, item 5 of the Ordinance on Inclusive Education (adopted by Council of Ministers Decree No. 286 of 2016) and in connection with Decision No. 373 of July 5, 2017, which establishes a Mechanism for the joint work of institutions to ensure the enrollment and retention of students in the educational system during the mandatory preschool and school age.

The primary role of the educational Mediator is to serve as an intermediary between families, local communities, children, students, kindergartens, and schools, thereby facilitating enrollment, social inclusion, and integration. This role also aims to improve the quality of preschool and school education for children and students from vulnerable groups within the educational institution. Additionally, the educational mediator supports the active involvement of the local community and parents in the development of education and the personal advancement of their children.

As part of their responsibilities within the educational institution, the educational mediator organizes and implements activities aimed at ensuring students' regular school attendance and their full participation in the educational process. Additionally, the mediator facilitates initiatives that engage parents and the local community in the educational and social life of students.

The mediator assists in the enrollment and retention of students subject to compulsory education, visits students' families, and conducts discussions with parents/guardians to provide information and enhance motivation for continuing education. This role is particularly crucial when students belong to minority and/or marginalized groups/communities and are bilingual children. Furthermore, the mediator supports communication between pedagogical specialists and students, and takes part in resolving disputes that arise within the educational institution involving students.

Another key function of educational mediators is to act as a bridge between educational institutions, local communities, and students who are often at risk of early school dropout. The lack of education and social isolation of these students create conditions for future economic instability, increased long-term unemployment, and reduced competitiveness of human resources. In this context, school mediation can be seen as a means of minimizing long-term risks to national security by fostering educated and resilient citizens (Moore, 2014).

The present study proposes a new conceptual framework for analyzing educational mediation, defined as the "Consensus-based educational mediation model" (Lyudmilov, 2024). This model presents educational mediation as a mechanism for achieving consensus within the educational environment, based on the integration of legal and institutional mechanisms.

In this framework, two main domains of educational mediation can be distinguished:

- **First Domain: Legal consensus in education** – This refers to the application of legal mediation, the integration of regulatory documents, and the work of the Ministry of Education and Science (MES), as well as the legal framework for protecting the rights of students and pedagogical specialists.

- **Second Domain: Institutional consensus in education** – This encompasses mutual dialogue, the interaction between educational institutions and local authorities, as well as the psychological dimensions of the mediation process, which involve layered psychological factors.

The interaction between these domains leads to the formation of two main **cause-and-effect frameworks**:

I. Administrative Consensus – *Based on legally established mechanisms for conflict management in the educational environment, including the application of legal procedures and institutional regulations.*

II. Social Inclusion – *A result of the implementation of educational mediation within the context of social policies aimed at integrating vulnerable groups and reducing social inequalities in the educational system.*

The **broader legal context** of educational mediation encompasses not only the specific provisions of school education but also additional legislative and regulatory frameworks related to **social rights and social protection policies**. This includes:

a) The child protection act and the social assistance and services act, which regulate the rights of children within the educational process.

b) National and international legal frameworks for data protection and consumer rights, which are essential for participation in international educational programs and mobility.

c) The Convention on the rights of the child, which establishes principles for the protection and support of children within the educational environment.

In this context, educational mediation plays a key role in establishing administrative consensus while also serving as a mechanism for social inclusion through effective interaction among students, teachers, parents, and institutions.

Figure 1. Consensus-based educational mediation model (Lyudmilov, 2024). Author's Own Work.

Description: Figure 1 presents the theoretical framework for analyzing educational mediation proposed by the author. The model illustrates the two main domains: legal consensus (regulatory and legal mechanisms) and institutional consensus (interactions between institutions and the educational environment). The interaction between these domains establishes administrative consensus and promotes social inclusion as a strategic approach to managing educational conflicts.

This conceptual framework expands existing research on educational mediation by presenting it not only as a conflict resolution tool but also as a strategic mechanism for institutional governance and legal regulation of social inclusion in education.

An important element for the effective implementation of mediation in educational institutions is the mediator's knowledge and approach toward psycho-pedagogy and general psychology (including sociology). This knowledge is essential for the mediator to establish a clear, sustainable, and logical connection be-

tween the emerging issue in the school and the student(s), with the aim of fostering social inclusion and overcoming barriers in the educational process.

A deep understanding of the student's social environment – family, close relatives, friends, past life experiences, social participation, and potential childhood traumas – is essential for building a successful mediation practice in schools. These factors often have a significant impact on a student's behavior in school and can be key triggers for aggression and demotivation toward continuing education. By recognizing these influences, mediators and educators can create a supportive and inclusive environment that helps students navigate challenges and remain engaged in their educational journey.

In a detailed analysis of educational mediation, three main parallel branches of its two core domains can be distinguished – educational (First Branch), socio-cultural (Second Branch), and legal (Third Branch)—as presented below.

Figure 2. Branches of educational mediation (Lyudmilov, 2024). Author's Own Work.

a) **First Branch** – Related to the hierarchy within the educational institution, which includes: (a) *Principal*, (b) *Teachers*, and (c) *Students*.

b) **Second Branch (Society)** – Examines the factors influencing the student's attitude toward education, including:

i. *Family – Both primary and extended (e.g., grandparents caring for the child in the absence of parents);*

ii. *Relatives, friends, and social contacts; iii. Social media and civil society.*

c) **Third Branch** – Encompasses the legislative framework and the hierarchy of public administration:

i. *Regulatory acts of the Ministry of Education and Science (MES); ii. General school rules; iii.*

Ethical code; iv. Professional conduct and a high level of confidentiality.

The three components offer a systematic approach to understanding the processes of educational mediation and their interaction with various social structures. This enables mediators, educational institutions, and sectoral policies not only to address individual conflicts in schools but also to develop sustainable strategies for social inclusion.

b) Social marginalization and school dropout as destabilizing factors

Social marginalization and early dropout from the educational system pose serious challenges that affect not only individuals but also the overall economic stability of society. According to Daskalova (2017), the lack of quality education is a key factor contributing to the social isolation of vulnerable groups, often leading to high levels of poverty and unemployment. Empirical studies conducted in various countries indicate that educational deprivation increases the risk of social exclusion and correlates with a higher tendency toward criminal behavior.

Following this line of reasoning, a logical connection can be made that early dropout from the educational system may lead to the formation of a vulnerable group of individuals who will later face significant challenges in integrating into the labor market. The social isolation of young people resulting from a lack of education creates conditions for long-term economic instability, reduced employment opportunities, and an increased risk of social conflicts. All of this ultimately contributes to a heightened risk of radicalization and extremism among young people.

From the perspective of national security, the lack of educational integration and inclusion of marginalized groups can lead to the formation of social segregation and an increase in tension between different social and ethnic communities in the country. Unequal access to education and social inclusion is one of the main reasons for deepening social divisions and conflicts. In this context, educational mediation plays a key role in overcoming these negative processes by creating channels for interaction and communication between students in the classroom and society.

c) Prevention of social conflicts in the school environment through mediation mechanisms

The educational environment often serves as a microcosm of society, where social conflicts arise due to cultural, socio-economic, and ethnic differences. In this sense, the school can be both a generator of social conflicts and an environment for their effective management/resolution. Educational mediators play a fundamental role in fostering positive social attitudes and preventing conflicts through several key mechanisms:

- **Communication strategies** that are designed to develop dialogical models, promoting intercultural communication and understanding between different social groups.

- **Mediation sessions**, through the introduction of systematic conflict resolution programs in schools, allow students to acquire skills for non-violent communication and the building of social connections.

- **Institutional cooperation**, providing an opportunity for the inclusion of the local community, non-governmental organizations, and public institutions in the process of social integration through the mechanisms of educational mediation.

- **Educational policies** aimed at developing educational programs that encourage the formation of social responsibility and a culture of peaceful coexistence.

The application of the tools and mechanisms of mediation in the school environment can significantly contribute to reducing levels of aggression, discrimination, and social alienation among students, creating conditions for a more sustainable and safe educational environment, where the school becomes a desired space.

CONCLUSION

Educational mediation should not be viewed solely as a tool for reducing school conflicts but rather as a strategic mechanism for strengthening social stability and national security. Through the systematic application of mediation approaches in schools, state institutions can prevent a range of long-term social and economic issues, including crime, radicalization, and unemployment.

In this sense, investments in educational mediation not only contribute to a more effective and inclusive educational system but also help build sustainable national security based on social integration and economic stability.

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